

A Retrospective study HMIS data for improvement of MCH Services at Tertiary care center.

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Received: 03-01-2024 / Revised: 16-01-2024 / Accepted: 29-01-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Health Management Information System (HMIS) is a web-based monitoring information system that has put in place by Ministry of Health and Family welfare to monitor National Health Mission and other health programmes and to provide inputs for policy formulation and appropriate programme interventions. With the growing importance of health in the global agenda, health management information system (HMIS) has emerged as one of the key activities that require accelerated efforts to meet international as well as country specific needs.

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Introduction

The HMIS web portal was launched in October, 2008 to enable capturing data from both public and private institutions in rural and urban areas across the country. The portal is envisaged as a “Single Window” for all public health data for the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare.

Accessibility to Maternal and Child Health Services refers to the ability to access and benefit from HMIS offered by a country's health system. Many global, regional, and national healthcare strategic efforts aim to minimize mother and newborn morbidity and mortality.[1]

An effective health management information system (HMIS) that gathers accurate, consistent, and relevant data in a timely manner can improve health program planning, monitoring, and service delivery, increasing the effectiveness of interventions[2]

Objectives

To Analyse the trend of services provided in Government General Hospital, Anantapur in respect to that of maternal health services provided by Department of Gynaecology and Obstetrics over 3-year period that is from 2018-19, 2019-20, 2020-21

Materials and method

Study setting: GGH, Ananthapur , A.P.

Study Period: 01.04.2018 to 31.03.2021.

Type of study: Retrospective Observational study

Study subjects: HMIS data

Ethical consideration:

The study was conducted after getting permission from the institutional review board (IRB) of Government Medical college, Ananthapur.

Methods

The present retrospective analysis of data was routinely uploaded into the Health Management Information System (HMIS) by health care personnel from 01.04.2018 to 31.03.2021. Data was analysed in respect to institutional deliveries, treatment of severe anemia, cesarean sections, late night cesarean sections, eclampsia, still born, medical termination of pregnancy less than 12 weeks, more than 12 weeks, neonatal deaths, maternal deaths were analysed using simple percentage according to the data uploaded in the HMIS portal.

Results

Table 1: Indicator wise data distribution during the 2018-19, 2019-20, and 2020-22

	Indicator	2018-2019 (%)	2019-2020 (%)	2020-2021 (%)
1	Institutional deliveries	9195	9392	8093
2	Treatment of severe anemia	1044 (11.35)	1520 (16.18)	955 (11.8)
3	C-sections	3336 (36.28)	3744 (39.86)	3494(43.17)
4	Late night C-sections	561 (6.1)	613 (6.53)	762 (9.42)
5	Eclampsia	211 (2.29)	131 (1.39)	168 (2.08)
6	Still birth	293 (3.19)	254 (2.7)	255 (3.15)
7	MTP < 12 weeks	114 (1.24)	121 (1.28)	150 (1.85)
8	> 12 weeks	150 (1.63)	153 (1.63)	150 (1.85)
9	Neonatal Deaths< 4 weeks	486 (5.29)	429 (4.57)	373 (4.61)
10	Maternal deaths	20 (0.22)	20 (0.21)	15 (0.18)
11	Obstetrics Complications attended	546 (5.94)	249 (2.65)	220 (2.72)

Figure 1: Indicator wise data distribution during the 2018-19, 2019-20, 2020-21

This is a retrospective study done by using the HIMS data of the years of 2018-19, 2019-20 and 2020-21. Total Institutional Deliveries were highest during 2019-20 i.e. 9392 and minimum 8093 were in the year of 2020-21. Total treated Anaemia cases were highest during 2019-20 i.e. 16.18% and 11.8% were the minimum during the 2020-21. During the year 2020-21 performed highest number of C-section and minimum C-section done in the year of 2018-19. C-sections were constantly rose from 2018-19 to 2020-21 from 36.28% to 43.17%. Late night C-sections were also had the same trend like C-sections. During the study period still birth rate was highest during the 2018-19 years and lowest recorded during the year 2019-20. MTPs rate was

constantly increasing from 2018-19 to 2020-21 from 1.24% to 1.85%. Neonatal death rate was constantly decreased from 2018-19 to 2020-21 from 5.29% to 4.61%. During the study period maternal death rate was constantly decreasing from the year 2018-19 to 2020-21 from 0.22% to 0.18%. Obstetrics complications treated during the year 2018-19 was highest and minimum was during the year 2020-21.

Discussion

In this study, Retrieving HMIS data for improvement of MCH Services at Tertiary care center. Despite decades of obstetric care advancements, maternal morbidity and mortality in developing nations persist.[3] Maternal morbidity, which is

undocumented, is larger than maternal mortality. A quantitative study of the reports from the Health Management Information System (HMIS) revealed that the majority of the maternal and child health services that were utilized by the beneficiaries had a downward trend.[4] MIS data that is utilized in program evaluations could be improved through ongoing regular data quality checks, the promotion of the use of HMIS data for quality improvement in health care delivery at the facility level, and training to address gaps in the data

Conclusions

There was no variable HMIS data quality by data element, with some indicators with high quality and consistency in reporting trends across study period. Underreporting was observed for the year 2018-19 in ANC related data. Even though novel corona virus COVID -19 had disrupted the service providers all over the world, but its impact on maternal health care services by Government General Hospital, Anantapur is minimal or negligible. In fact, some of services has increased during the study period. Data quality assessments

and training to address the gaps could help improve HMIS data quality

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